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PERSISTENCE OF HUMAN ISOLATE OF *P. AERUGINOSA* IN VEGETABLE CROPS*

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Summary: Increased usage of raw vegetables, without heat treatment, in human nutrition carries the risk of possible infection by pathogenic bacteria. The possibility of persistence of human isolates in vegetable crops represents, in epidemiological sense, a serious source of infection. The aim of this research was to study the possibilities of persistence of human isolates of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in selected vegetable crops, as well as the possibility of bacterial transport from roots to the above-ground part of the plant. Obtained results confirmed the possibility of persistence of human isolates of *P. aeruginosa* in the aforementioned vegetables.

Key words: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, persistence, vegetable crops.

INTRODUCTION

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is a ubiquitous bacterium that is one of most frequent causes of opportunistic human infections (Stover et al., 2000). It causes alimentary infections and it is considered as one of the main causes of nosocomial infections in immunocompromised patients (Bodey et al., 1983). The ability of some strains of *P. aeruginosa* to cause infections in humans, animals and plants is based on a large number of virulence factors, the possibility of forming a biofilm (Costerton et al., 1999) and different mechanisms of resistance to antimicrobial drugs (Chuanchuen et al., 2001). Biofilm makes bacteria resistant to disinfectants, antibiotics and mechanisms of host immune response (Koch and Høiby, 1993; Costerton et al., 1999).

Pseudomonas aeruginosa was also identified as a cause of pathological changes in lettuce, tobacco, bananas, onion and other plants (Lebeda et al., 1984). The occurrence of pseudotuberculosis, yersiniosis, listeriosis and

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intestinal infections in the usage of raw vegetables, fruits and meals prepared of them was reported in epidemiological studies (Djukic et al., 2011). Research carried by Kominos et al. (1972) shows the high level of contamination by this bacterium in raw vegetables prepared in hospital kitchens which leads to the conclusion that the vegetables are the primary source of infection by this bacterium. Significant reduction of alimentary infections by *P. aeruginosa* in hospitals followed the elimination of fresh vegetables from the patients' diets (Green et al., 1974). Therefore, the consumption of vegetables contaminated by this bacterium can seriously impact human health.

The aim of this study was to investigate the possibility of persistence of human isolates of *P. aeruginosa* in plants that can be used unprocessed in human nutrition.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study included four types of vegetable plants: cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L.), cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata* L.), tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) and pepper (*Capsicum annuum* L.), grown from seeds of the Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops in Novi Sad. The used strain of *P. aeruginosa* was isolated from human throat swabs and identified in the Center for Microbiology of the Institute of Public Health of AP Vojvodina. The experiment was set up in the Laboratory of Microbiology and Parasitology, Faculty of Agriculture in Novi Sad.

Sowing containers with 56 places filled with sterile substrate (autoclaved for 45 minutes at 121 °C at pressure of 1.2 atm) were used for performing the experiment. The experiment was set up in three replications with 4 plants. Before sowing the seeds were disinfected by immersion in 75% alcohol for 15 minutes, then in sterile distilled water for 10 minutes and after that rinsed with distilled water for 5 minutes. Seeds of all species were sown on the 16th of December 2013 and by occurrence of cotyledon leaves (cabbage and cucumber after 10 days, 19 days of tomatoes, and peppers 25 days after sowing) injecting of bacterial suspensions in the zone of the root system of plants was performed. For the preparation of bacterial suspension concentration of 6×10^8 cfu ml⁻¹ (2th scale by McFarland (Clement et al., 1990) of the overnight culture were used. Quantity of the bacterial suspension were 2 ml and the injection was carried out by using a syringe and medical needle. Plants were grown in phytotron with regular irrigation with sterile water.

After 15 days of injection of the suspension into the zone of the root system, the separation of the above-ground parts of plants without touching the substrate was carried out. Removed plant material was macerated with 1 ml of sterile distilled water and then inoculated on nutrient agar and incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C. Identification of isolated bacteria was done using standard biochemical tests. Both human and plant isolates were tested for susceptibility to the following antimicrobials drugs: piperacillin/tazobactam, ceftazidime, cefepime, imipenem, meropenem, doripenem, gentamycin, amikacin and ciprofloxacin using disk diffusion technique by Kirby-Bauer on Muller-Hinton agar according to the recommendation of Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI, 2012).

Data processing was performed using the Statistica software 10, by using Tukey HSD test, level of significance of $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

The research indicates that the bacteria penetrate into the above-ground portions of the plants through the root system, without making pathological changes in plants. The isolated strains were identified as *P. aeruginosa*. The presence of *P. aeruginosa* was found in all 12 plants of cucumber and cabbage (100%), in 9 tomato plants (75%) and in 7 plants of pepper (58.3%) (Figure 1). By analyzing the infected plant a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the presence of *P. aeruginosa* between peppers and the other crops examined was found (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Number of infected plants per culture

Susceptibility of isolates originated from the inoculated plants, was identical to susceptibility of original human isolate. Based on these facts it may be considered that isolates obtained from plants and human isolate belong to the same strain.

DISCUSSION

The range of bacteria capable of living both in plants and in the human body is quite wide (Djukic et al., 2011). The same species of bacteria have the ability to cause the infection in humans, animals and plants. The examples are specific strains of *P. aeruginosa* as the strain UCBPP-PA14 (PA14) which causes disease in plants of *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Rahme et al., 1997), insect *Drosophila melanogaster* (Jander et al., 2000), mice (Rahme et al., 1995), and nematodes *Caenorhabditis elegans* (Mahajan-Mikloset et al., 1999). The ability of bacteria to survive in plants, raises the question whether plants can be reservoirs of human and animal pathogens? This fact is very significant, particularly for vegetable crops which are used without heat treatment, and therefore can be a direct source of alimentary infections. Transmission of pathogenic bacteria to plants is possible by using contaminated water, inadequate compost, fresh manure, liquid manure and feces of wild animals (Natvig et al., 2002, Santamaria and Toranzos, 2003; Tyrrel et al., 2006).

It is considered that the two factors of the virulence of *P. aeruginosa*, exotoxin A and phospholipase C, influence the occurrence of systemic spread of infection in mammals and *Arabidopsis*. By the analysis of the genome of *P. aeruginosa* it has been established that at least three genes encoding the virulence factors are involved in the pathogenesis of plants and animals (Rahme et al., 1995). The research carried out by Jander et al. (2000) indicates that the gene MucD is an important virulence factor for plants, insects, nematodes and mammals, and that the MucD gene is required for production of extracellular toxins C (Yorgey et al., 2001). The opinion is that trehalose plays a crucial role as a virulence factor during infection of leaves of plants (Djonović et al., 2013). It is assumed that *P. aeruginosa* parasitizes in parenchymal tissue of the plants (Plotnikova et al., 2000).

CONCLUSION

On the basis of our experiment, it can be concluded that *P. aeruginosa* has the ability to persist in cucumbers, cabbage, tomato and pepper. All isolates from the inoculated plants originate from the injected human isolate, which suggests the possibility of migration of bacteria from the roots in aboveground vegetative part. Consumption of infected plants may be an important way of infecting humans and domestic animals with *P. aeruginosa*.

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PREZISTENCIJA HUMANOG IZOLATA *PSEUDOMONAS AERUGINOSA* U POVRĆU

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Izvod: Povećana upotreba sirovog povrća, bez termičke obrade, u ljudskoj shrani nosi rizik od moguće infekcije sa patogenim bakterijama. Mogućnost perzistencije humanog izolata u biljnim kulturama predstavlja u epidemiološkom smislu, ozbiljan izvor zaraze. Cilj ovog istraživanja je bio ispitivanje mogućnosti perzistencije humanog izolata *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* u odabranim povrtarskim kulturama, kao i mogućnost transporta bakterije iz korena u nadzemni deobiljke. Dobijeni rezultati potvrđuju mogućnost perzistentnosti humanog izolata u odabranim povrtarskim kulturama.

Ključnereči: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, perzistencija, povrće.

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